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Optimization Techniques for Multi- Agent Systems

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Abstract—Intelligent buildings are responsible for ensuring the indoor air quality for their occupants under normal operation as well as under possibly harmful contaminant events due to accidental or malicious actions. An emerging environmental control application is monitoring the intelligent buildings against the presence of such events, by incorporating various sensing technologies and distributed detection and isolation algorithms. The needed simplicity, the improved scalability and fault tolerance are some of the main reasons for choosing distributed approaches over centralized ones. Hence, the effective partitioning of buildings into smaller sections for contaminant detection and isolation approaches is of great importance. In this paper, we present an exact Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formulation for partitioning the building into smaller sections. The building is transformed into a graph which is partitioned into subgraphs indicating the groups of zones in each section while ensuring (i) maximum decoupling between the various subgraphs, (ii) strong connectivity between the zones of a subgraph and (iii) control of the number of allocated zones in each subgraph. The main contribution of this work is the automatic partitioning of the building into sections, which enables the distributed simulation, modeling, analysis and management of the intelligent building in real time, while ensuring the effective detection and isolation of contaminants in the building interior.

I. INTRODUCTION

Intelligent buildings are responsible for controlling their occupants' comfort, health, productivity and safety. Studies have shown that airborne contaminants which are either generated indoors, or penetrate into the indoor environment from outside sources, are some of the main causes of Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) related problems [1], [2]. Random, every day accidents or targeted malicious acts, can lead to such health-threatening contaminant events. For the protection of occupants in such events, the prompt application of contaminant detection and isolation approaches is required.

In our previous work [3], [4], we developed a state space method using a multi-zone formulation for the problem of contaminant event monitoring in smart buildings. In this framework, the building is characterized by the number of zones (e.g. rooms) and the airflows between them that are created by natural (wind) or forced ventilation (fans). Thus, the building can be described as a system with interacting zones that can potentially transport air contaminants between its zones. In the proposed formulation, through advanced fault diagnosis methods we are able to detect and isolate (determine the source zone) the contaminant event which is modeled as a fault in the process. Furthermore, in [4] we developed a Contaminant Detection and Isolation (CDI) estimator scheme with adaptive thresholds for the detection and isolation of a

single contaminant source in the presence of measurement noise and modeling uncertainty.

Due to the computational problems that emerge in centralized approaches as in [3], [4], our efforts subsequently shifted towards the development of distributed approaches for contaminant detection and isolation in smart buildings. On this notion, distributed approaches have shown significant benefits over the centralized ones due to (i) the simplicity of smaller subsystems, (ii) improved scalability and (iii) increased reliability due to the lack of a single point of failure [5]. In particular, a distributed CDI scheme is presented in [6], where we consider the building as a collection of interconnected subsystems. Buildings offer a natural candidate for such structural partitioning, because they are distributed in space and a particular building zone is only interconnected with a limited number of neighboring zones, mainly through doors and windows. Despite the clear advantage of the distributed CDI approaches, their successful deployment relies on the proper partitioning of the building into individual subsystems; note that [6] does not specify exactly how the building partitioning

should be performed. Furthermore, in order to maximize the effectiveness of CDI algorithms, the system should be partitioned in such a way as to (i) minimize the coupling between the various subsystems in terms of the airflows, (ii) ensure connectivity inside the various subsystems so that all zones of a subsystem are connected through at least one airflow and (iii) fairness with respect to the number of zones allocated to each subsystem. Most importantly, in a real building setting, the airflows may often change due to variable environmental conditions (temperature, wind direction and velocity), as well as the opening and closing of doors and windows. Therefore, the partitioning algorithm should also be able to quickly adapt and regroup the building zones under these conditions.

In this paper, an exact Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formulation for the structural partitioning of buildings is proposed, that addresses the building partitioning problem introduced in [6]. The proposed MILP, uses the airflows between the zones as a measure of their dependencies and partitions the building into individual subsystems by employing a novel way of adaptively defining a source zone in every resulting subsystem. The selected sources are then combined with the theory of network flows, to ensure that the formed subsystems are connected. Based on the work presented in [6], the modeling uncertainties and the interconnection uncertainties strongly depend on the airflows between the zones; hence by minimizing the airflows between the subsystems and controlling their size, the effective application of the distributed contaminant detection and isolation approaches is ensured. The proposed approach, targets specifically the building decomposition problem. Although oriented in building partitioning, the MILP formulation is able to combine multiple constraints which are easily added thanks to its versatile nature, providing *full* control over the solution and rendering it capable of adapting to other applications as well.

Partitioning techniques have been widely applied in many fields. Despite the fact that the basic objective of these techniques is the same (the formation of subsystems), they can be encountered by different names (decomposition, clustering, grouping, partitioning etc.) depending on the application field. One could distinguish the various techniques in two categories: (i) The techniques that consider the system (the building) as a whole and they try to separate it into subsystems (decomposition and partitioning) and (ii) The techniques that consider the individual parts (the building zones) of the system and try to group them in order to form the subsystems (clustering, grouping). Even though they are very similar, there is no universal solution that can deal with all decomposition problems, since, the vast majority of approaches are subject to different constraints and objective functions. In addition, an

impossibility theorem is presented in [7], which states the difficulty in the development of a universal clustering scheme.

In our previous work [8], we presented a heuristic algorithm based on matrix reordering techniques for the automatic building partitioning for Contaminant Detection and Isolation. The heuristic provides high quality solutions in a limited time frame. However, in order to evaluate its results, an exact solution is needed. The buildings can easily be modeled as graphs, where each zone corresponds to a vertex and an airflow path connecting two zones indicates the existence of an edge between them. The most relevant techniques that we found in the literature are the graph partitioning schemes. Their objective is to partition an initial graph into subgraphs by removing a number of its edges. It is worth mentioning that many fast heuristic algorithms for large graphs can be found in the literature (see for example [9]–[12]). However, they cannot offer the same level of control and accuracy as exact algorithms. Examples of exact algorithms can be found in [13]–[15], where they mainly target and find exact solutions for the balanced bisection problem, while also providing bounds for a small number of other resulting partitions. Note that, since the problem is NP-Hard, exact algorithms can only target relatively small problems. These algorithms include various size constraints, however, to the best of the authors' knowledge they do not consider the connectivity of the resulting partitions explicitly which is one of the main constraints in the building partitioning problem.

Nonetheless, connected subsystems have been explicitly investigated in other graph partitioning approaches. In [16], connectivity is preserved by successively exploring clusters of nodes called fronts and in combination with an iterative method, connected subgraphs are constructed. The theory of network flows has also been a major contributor of exactly modeling connectivity in graph partitioning problems, but not without some shortcomings. Connectivity preservation using network flows implies that, a source node has to be chosen, which is responsible of initiating the procedure of sending units of flow to all the other nodes that will act as sinks [17]. However, in the general case, the source nodes in each partition are not known a priori. Solution to a special case where only one subset is formed from a set of vertices, was given in [18]. Even though it generalizes in respect to the choice of vertices, it only provides one subset and it requires the addition of more binary variables; hence raises significantly the difficulty and lowers the tractability of the problem.

The organization of this paper is as follows: Section II introduces the problem of automatic building partitioning and gives an overview of the problem objective and constraints. Section III presents the exact MILP formulation and analyzes the size constraint impact to the partitioning cost. Section IV

compares the results of MILP and our heuristic algorithm in terms of quality of results and execution time for a realistic building case study and Section V concludes the paper.

Notation: Throughout the paper, calligraphic letters denote sets, the superscript $(\cdot)^T$ denotes the transpose and $|\cdot|$ denotes the cardinality.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

Consider an n -zone building as a centralized system, where the contaminant dispersion in the indoor environment of the building is described by the following multi-zone model:

$$\Sigma : \dot{\chi}(t) = (A + \Delta A)\chi(t) + Q^{-1}Bv(t) + Q^{-1}\Gamma\gamma(t) \quad \psi(t) = C\chi(t) + \omega(t),$$

where $\chi \in \mathbb{R}^n$ represents the concentration of the contaminant in the building zones, while $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the state transition matrix with its elements $A_{i,j}$ modeling the changes in contaminant concentration between zone i and zone j , primarily as a result of the air-flows; note that $A_{i,j} = 0$ if there is no leakage path connecting zones i and j . The term $\Delta A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ collectively accounts for the presence of modeling uncertainty in the building envelope as a result of the changing wind speed, wind direction and variable leakage openings. The controllable inputs in the form of doors, windows, fans and air handling units are represented by $v \in \mathbb{R}^p$, while $B \in \mathbb{B}^{n \times p}$ is a zone index matrix concerning their location, with $B = \{0, 1\}$. The last term describes the contaminant sources with respect to their location and evolution function, represented by $\Gamma \in \mathbb{B}^{n \times s}$ and $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^s$ respectively, and $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is a diagonal matrix that holds the volumes of the various zones. The outputs of the sensors monitoring Σ are represented by $\psi \in \mathbb{R}^m$, while $C \in \mathbb{B}^{m \times n}$ is a zone index matrix for the sensor locations and $\omega \in \mathbb{R}^m$ characterizes the additive measurements of noise.

Now consider the same building, decomposed into K interconnected subsystems $\Sigma_I, I \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, where each subsystem consists of n_I zones. The corresponding distributed model for contaminant dispersion inside the building is given in [6] as:

$$\Sigma_I : \dot{\chi}_I(t) = (A_I + \Delta A_I)\chi_I(t) + Q_I^{-1}B_I v_I(t) + Q_I^{-1}\Gamma_I \gamma_I(t) + (H_I + \Delta H_I)\zeta_I(t) \quad \psi_I(t) = C_I \chi_I(t) + \omega_I(t),$$

where $\chi_I \in \mathbb{R}^{n_I}$ represents the contaminant concentration in the zones of subsystem Σ_I . Correspondingly, the controllable inputs in the form of doors, windows, fans and air handling units are represented by $v_I \in \mathbb{R}^{p_I}$, the local measured output by $\psi_I \in \mathbb{R}^{m_I}$ and the vector of interconnection variables by $\zeta_I \in \mathbb{R}^l$. The term $\gamma_I \in \mathbb{R}$ represents the local contaminant source, $\Gamma_I \in \mathbb{R}^{n_I}$ represents the location zone of the contaminant source and

$\omega_I \in \mathbb{R}^{m_I}$ corresponds to the local noise vector. Terms, $A_I, \Delta A_I, B_I, Q_I, \Gamma_I$ and C_I are sub-matrices of the appropriate dimensions of the corresponding matrices of the centralized system Σ . Finally, H_I and ΔH_I are submatrices of A_I and ΔA_I respectively that account for the interconnection uncertainties (related to the interconnection variables ζ_I).

The objective of this work is to provide an automatic algorithm for forming the subsystems Σ_I while minimizing the flows that traverse between them; hence minimizing the interconnection effects $(H_I + \Delta H_I)$. By reducing the interconnection uncertainty, the residual bounds are also reduced leading to tighter adaptive thresholds for both the contaminant detector and isolator schemes described in [6]. Therefore, the time delay for contaminant detection and isolation is reduced and the overall performance of the approach is increased. Moreover, balancing the subsystems in terms of size, decreases the computational effort required by each individual subsystem. Note that the computational complexity of the contaminant detection and isolation schemes increases with the number of involved zones. In fact, when large buildings are considered, the calculation of the adaptive thresholds may become a formidable task.

Equivalently the problem of building partitioning can be described with graph theory where the building structure is transformed into a graph. Buildings, are a natural candidate for graph transformation since they are distributed in space and a particular zone is only connected with a limited number of surrounding zones. Each zone corresponds to a vertex while edges and weights correspond to the airflow paths and airflow magnitudes respectively.

Consider an undirected, connected graph $G = (V, E)$ and a matrix $D \in \mathbb{R}^{|V| \times |V|}$ for the edges weights $d_{i,j}, (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}_T$, defined in terms of the state transition matrix as $D = \frac{A+A^T}{2}$

Fig. 1. Airflow simulation example created using the CONTAM software.

	-451.178					133.922	
		-610.096					
			-1083.51	96.6373			874.886
				-193.275	80.0575		
					-80.0575		
		305.048	416.612			-721.659	
							-1974.98

Fig. 2. State transition matrix A corresponding to the airflow simulation example portrayed in Fig.1.

so that the edge weights become symmetrical (i.e. $d_{i,j} = d_{j,i}$, $i, j \in V$). Note that, the flow direction is not important for the partitioning problem. The objective is to partition the graph into $K \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ subgraphs $G_h = (V_h, E_h)$ where $\bigcup_h V_h = V$, $h \in K$ and $K = \{1, \dots, K\}$, indicating the subsystems while (i) minimizing the weight of the edges that are not included in any subgraph and defined as the *partitioning cost*:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E/h \in K} d_{i,j}$$

(ii) controlling the size of subgraphs and (iii) ensuring that each produced subgraph is connected. In addition, the resulting subgraphs must follow a minimum cardinality restriction as

$$|V_h| \geq M, h \in K \text{ where } M \in \mathbb{Z}^+.$$

1) *Building simulation example*: For demonstrating the problem formulation, we use a building simulation example created in CONTAM [19], a multizone airflow and contaminant transport analysis software. For the investigated scenario, we assume natural ventilation conditions with the wind blowing from the north-east while all the leakage paths (doors and windows) are in the fully open position. The building layout and the corresponding state transition matrix A for this particular scenario are portrayed in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively. The green lines in Fig. 1 represent the airflows (magnitude and direction) at the various leakage paths of the building while the airflow magnitudes are also included in the corresponding positions of the A matrix in Fig. 2. The diagonal elements of the A matrix represent the sum of incoming flows in each zone. Since they are not needed for partitioning the building, in the sequel they will be set to zero. By combining the information from Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 the building is transformed into a graph as depicted in Fig. 3.

III. EXACT MILP FORMULATION

In this section we describe the multi-constraint MILP formulation using the building simulation example introduced in the previous section. The formulation utilizes two sets of constraints. In the first set, “Basic partitioning constraints”, the graph is separated into different partitions. Next, connectivity is enforced by the “Connectivity constraints” set and the partitioning formulation is completed by two additional size constraints.

Following the buildings’ graph transformation in Fig. 3 and in order to minimize the *partitioning cost*, the objective function of the formulation is defined as:

(1)

Variables $z_{i,j} \in \mathbb{E}$ are defined as the capacity of the edge from i to j vertex where $z_{i,j} = 1$ if the edge is included in any subgraph and $z_{i,j} = 0$ otherwise. Variables $z_{i,j}$, are used for defining the objective function (1) and also afterwards for ensuring connectivity between vertices in each subsystem. If an edge is not included in a subgraph, it has a capacity of $z_{i,j} = 0$ and thus its weight $d_{i,j} \in \mathbb{E}$ is added in the *partitioning cost*. In contrast, if the edge is included in a subgraph, it has a capacity of $z_{i,j} = 1$ and a *partitioning cost* of 0.

Basic partitioning constraints

$$w_{i,j,h} \leq x_{i,h}, \quad (i,j) \in E, h \in K \quad (2a)$$

$$w_{i,j,h} \leq x_{j,h}, \quad (i,j) \in E, h \in K \quad (2b)$$

$$z_{i,j} = z_{j,i}, \quad (i,j) \in E \quad (2c)$$

$$z_{i,j} = \sum w_{i,j,h}, h \in K \quad (i,j) \in E \quad (2d)$$

$$x_{i,k} = 1, k \in K \quad i \in V \quad (2e)$$

$$x_{i,h} \geq M, \quad h \in K \quad (2f)$$

$$w_{i,j,h} \in [0, 1], z_{i,j} \in [0, 1], \quad (i,j) \in E, h \in K \quad (2g)$$

$$x_{i,h} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \in V, h \in K \quad (2h)$$

Basic partitioning constraints (2a)–(2h) describe the formation of subgraphs. The set of binary variables, $x_{i,h}$, $i \in V$, $h \in K$, indicate whether vertex i belongs to subgraph G_h . Auxiliary variables $w_{i,j,h}$, are used for connecting variables $x_{i,h}$ and $z_{i,j}$ in order to enforce the capacity on the edges.

Constraints (2a)–(2d) are used to enforce zero capacity on the links whose vertices belong to different subsystems. In order for an edge to have nonzero capacity, its vertices have to belong in the same subsystem. Moreover, equality (2e), ensures that a vertex is only included in one subgraph, while (2f) constraint guarantees the minimum cardinality ($|V_h| \geq M$, $h \in K$) of every subgraph.

Employing the Basic partitioning constraints (2a)–(2h) results in K subgraphs with minimum partitioning cost and cardinality of at least M . However, connectivity inside the subgraphs is not necessarily preserved; hence unconnected subgraphs may result. Therefore, the theory of network flows has been used in order to enforce their connectivity. Towards this direction, the selection of a source vertex in each subgraph was needed, for transmitting a unit of flow to the other vertices inside the same subgraph to ensure connectivity. The resulting subgraphs were not predetermined; hence the identification and selection of each source was not trivial. Also, since the problem

was already of exponential complexity, the addition of a new binary variable for indicating the source node would significantly decrease the solvability in relation to the problem's size. Therefore, a novel way of adaptively recognizing the source vertex based on the indices in each subgraph is formulated by the Connectivity constraints (3a)–(3i).

Continuous variable $f_{j,v,h}$ ($j,v \in E, h \in K$), indicates the amount of flow of the edge (j,v) that has as a source the vertex j and as a destination the vertex v for subgraph G_h . Variables $u_{j,h}$, $j \in V, h \in K$ and $y_{j,h}$, $j \in V, h \in K$ are auxiliary variables for defining the vertex that acts as a source in each subsystem and $y_h \in R^{|V|}, u_h \in R^{|V|}$, $h \in K$ define their respective vectors. The sources have been chosen to be the smallest index vertex in each subgraph.

To provide an illustration, consider the example of Fig. 3, where $K = 2$ and $M = 3$. It is easy to see that the subgraph borders would be at the edge connecting vertices 3 and 6. Note that, there are other better possible solutions with respect to the *partitioning cost* for 2 resulting subsystems, however for the purpose of this example the best solution with the minimum cardinality set to $M = 3$ is taken. Using vector $x_1 =$

$[0,0,1,1,1,0,1]^T$ which indicates the vertices that are included in V_1 in combination with constraints (3a) and (3b), the vector $y_1 = [0,0,1,1,1,1,1]^T$ is formed where the first non-zero element appears in the 3rd index. Clearly, the first non-zero element corresponds to the vertex with the smallest index in subgraph 1. In order to distinguish that particular vertex, constraints (3c)–(3e) are used, which result in $u_{3,1} = 1$ while $u_{j,1} = 0, j \in V \setminus \{3\}$. As a result, every subgraph is assigned a u_j vector consisting of a single non-zero element which indicates the vertex that is going to be used as a source for the connectivity conservation analysis.

Finally, the flow conservation constraint (3f) is used to enforce connectivity in each subgraph. The first term of (3f), is responsible for sending from the source as many units of flow as the number of vertices inside the subgraph. The second term shows that, every vertex consumes a unit of flow including the source nodes. The last two terms, represent the total inflow and the total outflow of the vertex. In the case where a subgraph is not connected, then, the equality will not be satisfied and the problem will be rendered infeasible. For the specific example shown in Fig. 3, the resulting subgraphs are derived through the final values of $x_{i,h}, h \in K$ vectors with vertex sets $V_1 = \{3,4,5,7\}$ and $V_2 = \{1,2,6\}$.

Although connectivity conservation is important, it appears to be necessary only when it is combined with the cardinality

constraint. Consider the example of Fig. 4. If the minimum cardinality of a subgraph is set to $M = 2$, it is clear that the only valid solution that follows the connectivity constraint subject to constraints (2a)–(2h), (3a)–(3i) is given by Cut 1 as indicated on the figure. However, if the Connectivity constraints (3a)–(3i) are not included, then the best possible solution is given by Cut 2, which results in an unconnected subgraph consisting of vertices 3 and 6. Finally, if both constraints of cardinality (2f) and connectivity (3a)–(3i) are excluded, then the solution is given by Cut 3. From the three cases, it can be deduced that without a minimum cardinality

Fig. 4. Example of results with both the constraints of connectivity and cardinality (Cut 1), with only the cardinality constraint (Cut 2) and with no constraint (Cut 3).

constraint, a smaller and connected subgraph would always exist and be better in terms of the *partitioning cost* than a subgraph formed from unconnected vertices. On the other hand, with a cardinality constraint there is the possibility that the optimal solution is unconnected (i.e Cut 2). Hence, the

Fig. 3. Example of a building transformation into a graph and the resulting subgraphs 1 & 2 after partitioning.

minimum cardinality constraint renders the enforcement of connectivity necessary in order to ensure that the resulting subgraphs are connected.

The presence of products of continuous and binary terms in (3f) makes the problem nonlinear and hence not suitable for Mixed Integer Linear/Quadratic Programming (MILP/MIQP) solvers. To resolve this issue, the first term of (3f) has been linearized. Considering that $u_{j,h}$ acts as a binary variable and $s_h = \sum_{i \in V} x_{i,h}$ is continuous with $M \leq s_h \leq L$ where $L = |V| - M(|K| - 1)$ and $M|K| \geq N$, the product $g_{j,h} = u_{j,h}s_h$ can be expressed with linear constraints yielding constraints (4a)–(4e).

Constraints of the maximum or the relative subgraph size have not been considered yet. Since, control over the resulting size attributes could significantly lower the contaminant

Linearization of constraint (3f)

$$s_h = \sum_{i \in V} x_{i,h} \quad h \in K \quad (4a)$$

$$Mu_{j,h} \leq g_{j,h} \leq Lu_{j,h} \quad j \in V, h \in K \quad (4b)$$

$$g_{j,h} \leq s_h - (1 - u_{j,h})M \quad j \in V, h \in K \quad (4c)$$

$$s_h - (1 - u_{j,h})L \leq g_{j,h} \quad j \in V, h \in K \quad (4d)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(g_{j,h} - x_{j,h}) + \\
 &+ \sum_{v \in V} f_{v,j,h} = \sum_{v \in V} f_{j,v,h} \quad j \in V, h \in K \quad (4e)
 \end{aligned}$$

detection and isolation algorithm’s computational restrictions, two new variables $B \geq 2$ and $R \in \mathbb{N}^+$ have been added as inputs and two additional constraints (5a) and (5b) have been incorporated into the formulation.

Constraint (5a), allows control of the maximum subgraph size in order to avoid having very large ones. Note, that in order for the maximum allowed subgraph size to alter the resulting solution then B should be chosen as $M < B < L$.

Although, unconstrained size leads to the best possible solution with respect to the cost function, the uncommon structures of the buildings often lead to very unbalanced solutions. Constraint (5b) allows control of the relative subgraph size, therefore leading to balanced solutions. Constraints (5a) and (5b) are meant to be used separately, according to the requirements of each problem. In the case that the two constraints are used together, B and R should be chosen carefully to avoid infeasible solutions.

Size constraints

$$s_h \leq B \quad h \in K \quad (5a)$$

$$-R \leq s_h - s_k \leq R \quad h, k \in K, h \neq k \quad (5b)$$

To summarize, the building partitioning problem is the minimization of the partitioning cost (1) subject to the Basic partitioning constraints (2a)–(2h), the Connectivity constraints (3a)–(3i) and the size constraint (5a) and/or (5b). Even though, the exact solutions of partitioning problems that include connectivity and size constraints are *NP – Hard* and hence of exponential complexity, they are valuable for finding solutions for small sized problems and for the proper evaluation of heuristic solutions obtained by other algorithms.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the MILP formulation. In the first set of experiments, we investigate how the number of resulting subgraphs K and the size constraints affect the overall solution. Furthermore, the MILP formulation is compared in terms of results and execution time with the heuristic algorithm presented in our previous work [8]. For the performance evaluation we use two building case studies: the Holmes¹ house with 14 zones and another residential house (DH15) with 21 zones. The flow matrices that have been used

¹ Refers to a low-rise residential house model used by J.D. Holmes and then scaled up for simulating airflow and contaminant transport [20].

for both buildings were constructed using the CONTAM software.

A. Effects of MILP Size Constraint

The MILP formulation can be easily adapted to different characteristics (i.e maximum size or relative size difference) of the resulting subgraphs as indicated by constraints (5a) and (5b). However the solutions are closely related to the bounds chosen for these constraints. The two constraints have been tested for the exact solutions of a house consisting of 21 rooms to show the effect of these constraints to the *partitioning cost*. The problem is modeled using YALMIP [21] and employs Gurobi [22] for the solution of the resulting MILP formulations.

Fig. 5. Comparison of solutions for different zone size constraints and different number of zones.

Fig. 5 incorporates constraint (5a) and shows the results for different number of resulting subgraphs (K) and also different size constraints for the maximum subgraph size. Also, the minimum size constraint has been set to $M = 2$. The solutions are affected by the overall number of subgraphs and also by the allowed maximum subgraph size. In the example, a solution with $K = 3$ for a house with 21 zones results in subgraph sizes of $2 - 2 - 17$ vertices with no size constraint. Imposing a maximum size constraint of $B = 7$ results in the more balanced subgraph sizes of $7 - 7 - 7$ vertices at a significant higher cost. The *partitioning cost* for the balanced solution is more than 10 times worse. In both cases the formulation takes advantage of the allowed subgraph size and provides a solution with as many subgraphs as possible having the maximum size. The tendency of subgraphs, to reach almost every time the size constraint, is

due to the unique characteristics of the buildings' structure. Since zones have a low degree of connectivity and

Fig. 6. Analysis of the fairness of the solution by relaxing the relative zone size difference.

some zones are connected with significantly lower airflows then, for a particular selection of a maximum size constraint, multiple subgraph possibilities with a low number of edges traversing between and low *partitioning cost* exist.

As far as the solutions for $B \leq 13$ are concerned, where all values of K appear to have almost the same *partitioning cost*, apart from the relatively small values of airflows, it is deduced that, the maximum size constraint is reached by at least one subgraph for every K . Thus, none of the results are considerably "limited" in terms of the *partitioning cost*, from the combination of maximum size constraint and number of subgraphs (K); hence similar results for multiple number of subgraphs are produced. Also, maximum size constraint implies that, the results for each number of resulting subgraphs (K) are becoming valid for $B \geq dN/Ke$.

In general, the number of resulting subgraphs K is inversely proportional to the *partitioning cost*. Moreover, the best solution for a specific number of subgraphs is generally achieved with $K-1$ subgraphs having 2 (minimum number) of vertices only and the last subgraphs having all the remaining vertices (remember the unique structure of houses).

Fig. 6 shows the effect of the relative size difference parameter for $R \in \{1, \dots, 20\}$ and for resulting subgraph sizes of $K \in \{2, \dots, 5\}$. From the results, it can be seen that the closer the size of the resulting subgraphs, the worse the solutions are with respect to the *partitioning cost*. In addition, there is always an almost equal or worse solution using a smaller number of subgraphs. Overall, there is an inevitable trade-off between the *partitioning cost* and fairness of the solution. The decision

regarding the degree of fairness, depends on the requirements of the individual application.

B. MILP and Heuristic Comparison

The heuristic algorithm presented in [8] follows a matrix reordering approach. It uses the state transition matrix A of

Fig. 7. Partitioning cost comparison of optimal MILP formulation and the Heuristic algorithm for houses of 14 and 21 zones.

Fig. 8. Comparison of mean execution time for MILP and the Heuristic algorithm for $K \in \{2, \dots, 7\}$. Since the Heuristic provides a range of results for different resulting number of subgraphs after one run, its execution time is presented as the same for every K .

the building as input and reorders the rows and columns in order to form blocks of values indicating the resulting subsystems. Its objective is to minimize the values that are left outside of any block and represent the flows between the subsystems. The heuristic can provide high quality results combined with size constraints in a limited time. However, it cannot ensure the optimality of the solutions. On the other hand, the MILP formulation offers complete control of the solution, its constraints are easily adjustable and ensures the optimality of the solution.

From the results of Fig. 7, it is deduced that for a small number of resulting partitions the heuristic provides results with the same *partitioning cost* as the MILP formulation. However,

the MILP formulation provides better results for 5 partitions in the 21 zone building example. The non optimal result of the heuristic algorithm for $K = 5$ is a clear indication about the importance of the exact solution.

In terms of execution time, the complexity of the problem increases with the number of constraints added. In order to test both algorithms, 200 random undirected graphs were generated with building characteristics as low node connectivity and connectivity only with neighboring nodes. The graphs consist of 30 nodes and 50 edges each, with random integer values $w \in [200;1000]$ for the edges' weights. The relative difference for the partition size was set to dN/Ke , where N is the number of zones and K is the number of the resulting partitions. Since the heuristic algorithm has no way of constraining the resulting number of partitions *a-priori* and the relative partition size, it was executed until it produced a valid result. The two approaches could not be compared in terms of execution time for each individual K , since the heuristic produces a range of solutions in every run. Therefore, the mean execution time for each K was calculated only for the MILP and compared with the resulting mean execution time of the heuristic. The execution times for both approaches appear in Fig. 8.

From the figure it can be seen that for $K \in \{2,3\}$ the execution time of MILP is much better than the heuristic. The execution time of MILP for $K \in \{4,5\}$ appears comparable with the execution time of the heuristic for all K . Where the heuristic execution time advantage becomes obvious is for $K \in \{6,7\}$, since on average, it provides results in noticeably less time. On the other hand, there is a trade-off between quality of the results and speed since, the heuristic does not always provide optimal results.

V. CONCLUSION

Contaminant event detection and isolation in multi-zone intelligent buildings is responsible for ensuring the occupants' health, productivity and safety. Successful deployment of such distributed approaches, requires a method for dividing the building into subsystems. In order to form the subsystems for the distributed CDI method presented in [6], in this paper we have developed a MILP formulation. It uses the state transition matrix of the CDI approach (which holds the airflows that connect the zones of the buildings) as the input adjacency matrix of the formulation and is able to partition the building graph into subgraphs indicating the subsystems. The formulation is able to minimize the subsystem interdependencies and preserve the initial connectivity while enforcing size constraints, which are all essential for increasing the performance of the CDI approach. In particular, controlling the results in terms of subsystem size can reduce computational

complexity and improve the performance of the contaminant detection and isolation method.

Future challenges include testing the formulation and evaluating its results in large-scale real buildings, incorporating the formulation in the CDI approach and considering its online implementation. Finally, estimating the probability of contaminant incident in each zone and incorporating it in the formulation is also an idea we are currently investigating.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Liu and Z. Zhai, "Inverse modeling methods for indoor airborne pollutant tracking: literature review and fundamentals," *Indoor Air*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 419–438, 2007.
- [2] X. Liu and Z. J. Zhai, "Prompt tracking of indoor airborne contaminant source location with probability-based inverse multi-zone modeling," *Building and Environment*, vol. 44, no. 6, pp. 1135 – 1143, 2009.
- [3] M. Michaelides, V. Reppa, C. Panayiotou, and M. M. Polycarpou, "Contaminant event monitoring in intelligent buildings using a multi-zone formulation," in *Fault Detection, Supervision and Safety of Technical Processes*, vol. 8, 2012, pp. 492–497.
- [4] M. Michaelides, V. Reppa, M. Christodoulou, C. Panayiotou, and M. Polycarpou, "Contaminant event monitoring in multi-zone buildings using the state-space method," *Building and Environment*, vol. 71, pp. 140 – 152, 2014.
- [5] J. Braun, "Intelligent Building Systems - Past, Present, and Future," in *American Control Conference*, 2007, pp. 4374–4381.
- [6] V. Reppa, M. Michaelides, M. Christodoulou, C. Panayiotou, and M. Polycarpou, "A distributed framework for contaminant event detection and isolation in multi-zone intelligent buildings," in *2014 European Control Conference (ECC)*, 2014, pp. 1637–1642.
- [7] J. Kleinberg, "An impossibility theorem for clustering," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, pp. 463–470, 2003.
- [8] A. Kyriacou, M. Michaelides, and C. Panayiotou, "Automatic building partitioning for effective contaminant detection and isolation." in *MELECON 2016*, Limassol, Cyprus, [to appear].
- [9] P. K. Chan, M. D. Schlag, and J. Y. Zien, "Spectral k-way ratiocut partitioning and clustering," *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, vol. 13, no. 9, pp. 1088–1096, 1994.
- [10] G. Karypis and V. Kumar, "Parallel multilevel series k-way partitioning scheme for irregular graphs," *Siam Review*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 278–300, 1999.
- [11] C. Aykanat, B. B. Cambazoglu, and B. Ucar, "Multi-level direct k-way hypergraph partitioning with multiple constraints and fixed vertices," *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 609–625, 2008.
- [12] R. Andersen, F. Chung, and K. Lang, "Local graph partitioning using pagerank vectors," in *47th Annual IEEE Symposium on Foundations of Computer Science, 2006. FOCS'06*. IEEE, 2006, pp. 475–486.
- [13] M. Boulle, "Compact mathematical formulation for graph partitioning," *Optimization and Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 315–333, 2004.
- [14] W. W. Hager, D. T. Phan, and H. Zhang, "An exact algorithm for graph partitioning," *Mathematical Programming*, vol. 137, no. 1-2, pp. 531–556, 2013.
- [15] L. Liberti, "Compact linearization for binary quadratic problems," *4OR*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 231–245, 2007.

- [16] J. Ciarlet, P. and F. Lamour, “On the validity of a front-oriented approach to partitioning large sparse graphs with a connectivity constraint,” *Numerical Algorithms*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 193–214, 1996.
- [17] B. Dilkina and C. Gomes, “Solving Connected Subgraph Problems in Wildlife Conservation,” in *Integration of AI and OR Techniques in Constraint Programming for Combinatorial Optimization Problems*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, A. Lodi, M. Milano, and P. Toth, Eds. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2010, vol. 6140, pp. 102–116.
- [18] T. Shirabe, “A model of contiguity for spatial unit allocation,” *Geographical Analysis*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 2–16, 2005.
- [19] G. N. Walton and W. S. Dols, “CONTAM 2.4 user guide and program documentation,” *National Institute of Standards and Technology, NISTIR*, vol. 7251, 2005.
- [20] L. L. Wang, W. S. Dols, and Q. Chen, “Using CFD capabilities of CONTAM 3.0 for simulating airflow and contaminant transport in and around buildings,” *HVAC&R Research*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 749–763, 2010.
- [21] J. Lofberg, “YALMIP : A Toolbox for Modeling and Optimization in MATLAB,” in *Proceedings of the CACSD Conference*, Taipei, Taiwan,